

THE PERFORMANCE OF *Litsea angulata* ESSENTIAL OIL FOR ANTI TERMITE ACTIVITY AGAINST SUBTERRANEAN TERMITES (*Macrotermes gilvus*)

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ABSTRACT. *Litsea angulata* from the Lauraceae Family is an aromatic plant that can produce essential oils from the forests of East Kalimantan, Indonesia. Aromatic plants can be toxic to insect pests, including termites, and can be used as an environmentally friendly alternative for anti-termite bioactivity. This research aims to determine the characteristics of essential oils of *L. angulata* leaves produced and their potential bioactivity to subterranean termites (*Macrotermes gilvus*). Essential oils are distilled by water and steam distillation method. The oil collected was the result of a 1-hour distillation process and yielded 0.32%. The results of the GC-MS identification show that the chemical components of the oil fraction of *L. angulata* are dominated by terpenoid compounds, with 3 major compounds, which are the main compounds, including Camphor, α -Phellandrene and α -Pinene. Bioactivity of anti termite was tested using a modified bioassay antifeedant method with a concentration variation of 0% (negative control), 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and fipronil 0,25% (positive control). The abundance of terpenoid group compounds is thought to have a great effect on anti-termite activity, with the quite strong effectiveness of *L. angulata* oil, with a percentage mortality rate ranging from 81-84%.

Keywords: Aromatic plant, *Litsea angulata* essential oil, Anti-termite activity, Bio-termite control

INTRODUCTION

The tropical rainforests of East Kalimantan are characterized by high biodiversity, including a wide range of aromatic plant species with significant medicinal properties. Among these, the *Litsea* genus, a member of the Lauraceae family, is widely distributed in Indonesia's tropical forests, with *Litsea angulata* being one of the most prevalent species. This genus is distinguished by its aromatic properties, with various plant parts, including leaves, twigs, and bark, producing essential oils. The essential oil derived from *Litsea* species has been recognized for its diverse applications, particularly in the pharmaceutical and agrochemical industries, with *L. angulata* showing potential as a valuable source of bioactive compounds [1].

The aromatic plants of tropical rainforests are largely driven by their bioactive properties, particularly their antimicrobial and insecticidal activities. Essential oils contain a variety of secondary metabolites, including terpenoids, flavonoids, and alkaloids, which contribute to their biological efficacy. Several studies have reported that these compounds exhibit toxic effects on insect pests, making essential oils a potentially alternative to synthetic insecticides [2]. The widespread use of synthetic pesticides has raised environmental concerns due to their persistence, bioaccumulation, and potential risks to non-target organisms, necessitating the exploration of environmentally sustainable pest control solutions [3].

Subterranean termites, particularly *Macrotermes gilvus*, are among the most economically significant pests in tropical regions. These termites cause extensive damage to wooden

structures, forestry resources, and agricultural crops, resulting in substantial economic losses. Conventional termite control strategies rely heavily on synthetic termiticides, which, despite their effectiveness, have been associated with environmental pollution and adverse health effects. As a result, there is an urgent need to develop plant-based termiticides that provide effective termite management while minimizing environmental and health risks [4]

Plant-derived extracts, including essential oils, have gained attention for their potential applications in wood preservation and insect pest management [5]. In Indonesia, the abundance and diversity of botanical resources present an opportunity for developing natural pesticides [6,7]. Essential oils from the *Litsea* genus, particularly *L. angulata*, contain major bioactive compounds from the monoterpene and sesquiterpene groups, which are known for their neurotoxic effects on insects, leading to increased mortality rates [8], [9]. However, no comprehensive study has yet been conducted on the chemical composition and anti-termite properties of *L. angulata* essential oil.

This research aims to optimize essential oil extraction through water and steam distillation, characterize its physicochemical properties, and evaluate its anti-termite bioactivity against *Macrotermes gilvus*. The findings are expected to contribute to developing sustainable, plant-based termite control alternatives.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

The *L. angulata* leaf samples were collected from the Education Forest Laboratory of Forestry Faculty, Mulawarman University, East Kalimantan, around ±10 kg. Leaf samples are sorted for distillation.

Water and steam distillation

The modified steam system distillation method uses a distillation boiler [10]. Leaf samples were air-dried for 24 hours and refined before extraction. Essential oil was obtained from the distillation process conducted for one hour. Essential oil that is still mixed with water is separated with sodium sulfate, and pure oil is collected in a vial bottle. The oil obtained is presented in percent yield, Eqn.1[11].

$$\text{Yield (w/w\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of essential oil (g)}}{\text{Weight of sample before extracting (g)}} \times 100$$

Eqn. 1

Physico-chemical characteristics of the extract

The physical properties of essential oils were analyzed for color by visual observation [12] and refractive index using a hand-refractometer [13].

The chemical compounds contained were analyzed by GC-MS (GC-MS-QP2010 Ultra Shimadzu). 0,5 ml of essential oil was put into a 50 ml volumetric flask, diluted with acetone, and then homogenized. Pipette as much as 3 ml into the vial. GC-MS instrument conditions: injector temperature 250°C with splitless mode, pressure 76,9 kPa, and flow rate 14 ml/min, ratio 1:10. Column type SH-Rxi-5Sil MS, column length 30 m, inner diameter 0.25mm. Total analysis time was 36 minutes. Compound compositions were reported as a percentage of peak area (%), and compounds were grouped by retention time and mass spectra, compared with standard spectra from the NIST library [14].

Termites

The workers and soldiers of *M. gilvus* were obtained from the field around the Faculty of Forestry, Mulawarman University. The colony was acclimatized for environmental adaptation.

Anti-termite bioactivity

A no-choice test evaluated anti-termite activity with an anti-feedant bioassay adapted and modified [15].

Fig. 1. Container termite test [16]

L. angulata oil was diluted in 70% alcohol, adding fixative oil to retain the aroma. It was then dropped on a test paper with a diameter of $\pm 4,5$ cm and air-dried to evaporate the solvent. The treatment involved varying concentrations of the essential oil at 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%. The negative control (0%) consisted of filter paper treated with 70% alcohol without essential oil, while the positive control used 0,25% of the chemical reagent fipronil.

The test container was filled with sterile sand, and the humidity was maintained by adding 5 ml of distilled water to the sand. Filter paper is placed on the moist sand. 50 termites, consisting of 45 workers and 5 soldier termites, were feeding. The test container was kept in a dark condition. Feeding was carried out for 14 days, and dead test termites were observed periodically. The observation parameters in evaluating effectiveness consist of termite mortality and weight loss of test paper (Eqn. 2, 3), [16].

$$\text{Weight-loss (\%)} = \frac{W1(g) - W2(g)}{W1 (g)} \times 100$$

Eqn. 2

Where, *W1*: Weight of paper test before feeding, *W2*: Weight of paper test after feeding

$$\text{Termite mortality (\%)} = \frac{\text{number of dead}}{50} \times 100$$

Eqn. 3

Data analysis

The data on the percentage of weight loss mortality of the test paper obtained were calculated by LC_{50} Analysis to determine the concentration of the test essential oil that can cause 50% mortality using the probit analysis method from the linear regression equation ($y = ax + b$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physico-chemical characteristics of the extract

The water and steam distillation of *L. angulata* leaves (1 hour) produced a greenish oil (Fig. 2). The oil from *L. angulata* leaves obtained a yield of 0,32% (Table 1). The refractive index measured by a hand refractometer was 1,411.

Table 1. Physical characteristics of the essential oil

Yield	Color	Refractive index
0,32%	Greenish	1,411

The water and steam distillation method is the most commonly used technique in the extraction of essential oils because steam is evenly distributed into the material network and the temperature can be maintained up to 100°C, so that the yield of oil obtained is greater and the quality is better than that of water distillation [17]. The coloured oils of essential oils are colourless when they are fresh and pure, but the colour can turn dark when long storage is done [18]. The refractive index is a measure that indicates the refraction of light between oil and air. The value of the refractive index is directly proportional to the water content contained in the oil; the higher the refractive index contained in an essential oil, the higher the water content value, which can reduce the quality of the oil [19].

Fig. 2. The essential oil from the leaves of *L. angulata*

GC-MS has evaluated twenty-five compounds. The chemical components were identified by comparing retention time, molecular formula, molecular weight, and percentage of area (Table 2). Three major component compounds, showing the highest percentage of other compounds, include Camphor (39,71%), α -Phellandrene (32,53%) and α -Pinene (4,28%).

The α -Phellandrene compound is a major compound with the most significant percentage area abundance derived from the monoterpene group. The α -Phellandrene compound is a cyclic monoterpene with two double bonds in a heterocyclic ring (endocyclic), which is very common in some essential oils, showing broad biological activity [20].

It is named after the plant species *Eucalyptus phellandra*, which was the first isolated plant to contain α -Phellandrene. α -Phellandrene is a natural plant-derived compound with a wide range of medicinal properties, useful in the pharmaceutical, food, cosmetics, and perfume industries [21,22]. Phellandrene compounds (PHE) are a source compound that produces fragrances. In particular [23], α -PHE shows the potential sources of bioactivity reported by [24] include anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-nosiseptic, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, and insecticide activity.

Table 2. Chemical compounds of *L. angulata* essential oil

No	RT ^a (Minutes)	Name of Compounds	MF ^b	MW (g/mol)	Area (%)
1	4,028	α -Pinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	4,28
2	4,224	Camphene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	0,40
3	4,570	β -Pinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	1,47
4	4,656	β -Myrcene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	0,74
5	4,923	α-Phellandrene	C₁₀H₁₆	136,23	32,53
6	4,987	3-Carene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	0,33
7	5,056	α -Terpinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	0,69
8	5,175	β -Cymene	C ₁₀ H ₁₄	134,23	5,66
9	5,230	(-)-Limonene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	2,76
10	5,426	<i>trans</i> - β -Ocimene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	0,35
11	5,630	γ -Terpinene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	0,54
12	6,065	α -Terpinolene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆	136,23	1,63
13	7,013	Camphor	C₁₀H₁₆O	152,23	39,71
14	7,660	α -Terpineol	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154,23	0,27
15	8,462	Limonene dioxide 1	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₂	168,23	0,70
16	8,870	9-Decen-2-one	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O	154,25	0,36
17	9,665	3-Hepten-2-one	C ₇ H ₁₂ O	112,17	0,50
18	10,291	α -Copaene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204,35	0,91
19	10,487	β -Elemene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204,35	0,47
20	10,951	<i>trans</i> -Caryophyllene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204,35	3,60
21	11,413	α -Humulene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204,35	0,48
22	11,853	Aromadendrene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204,35	0,43
23	11,961	(+)-Valencene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204,35	0,33
24	12,254	(+)- δ -Cadinene	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204,35	0,40
25	14,041	β -Eudesmol	C ₁₅ H ₂₆ O	222,36	0,46

Note: RT^a was Retention Time; MF^b was Molecular Formula; MW^c was Molecular Weight

Feeding the test filter paper for 7 days to subterranean termites resulted in various weight loss percentages for each oil concentration (Table 3). The higher the concentration of essential oil, the lower the weight loss percentage. Positive control shows that weight loss occurs at 0,19% or no feeding activity.

Table 3. Percentage weight loss of the test paper

Sample	Concentration	Weight-loss (%)	CV (%) ^{***}
<i>L. angulata</i> oil	25%	0,82 \pm 0,38	45,94
	20%	1,41 \pm 0,34	23,98
	15%	2,70 \pm 0,79	28,44
	10%	3,35 \pm 1,10	31,61
	5%	4,55 \pm 0,46	9,68
Fipronil*	0,25%	0,19 \pm 0,34	56,87
Control ^{**}	0%	6,32 \pm 0,64	9,57

Note: *(positive control); **(negative control); *** (percent coefficient of variation)

The optimum concentration (25%) showed the smallest percentage weight loss of 0,82%, and the lowest concentration of essential oil was 4,55%. The decreased feeding activity of subterranean termites influences the decrease in weight on the test paper. The feeding activity of subterranean termites decreases as the toxicity of *L. angulata* leaf essential oil increases, where the essential oil that has been applied is thought to inhibit the feeding activity of termites.

The extract of *L. angulata* contains the bioactive compound α -Phellandrene, a monoterpene with potential as a natural insecticide. [25] reported that this compound has a strong aroma and is toxic to insects. Its mechanism of action involves stomach poison, affecting the feeding behavior of termites, where physical damage to the termites correlates with the concentration of the extract. Research indicates that the mortality rate of termites reaches 100% after 3 days, demonstrating the high effectiveness of this extract [26].

After 7 days of feeding, the relationship of subterranean termite mortality to the concentration of the test essential oil shows that the high concentration indicates that the active compounds in the bait paper will be more abundant, causing high concentrations to show that high mortality.

Table 4. Mortality-rate

Sample	Concentration	Mortality (%)	CV (%)***	LC ₅₀ ****
<i>L. angulata</i> oil	25%	84 ± 4,00	4,76	17,65%
	20%	71 ± 4,16	5,84	
	15%	57 ± 3,06	5,39	
	10%	43 ± 3,06	7,05	
	5%	32 ± 3,46	20,83	
Fipronil*	0,25%	100 ± 0,00	0,00	-
Control**	0%	20 ± 2,00	10,00	-

Note: *(positive control); *(negative control); *(percent coefficient of variation); *(concentration that kills 50% of termites)

The highest mortality rate of subterranean termites, reaching 84%, was observed at the optimum concentration. According to [27], in evaluating the termite repellent classification level, 75-90% mortality is included in the strong group and is classified as very strong activity with a mortality range of $\geq 95\%$. The increasing concentration of extractive substances given has a positive correlation with termite mortality because the increasing active component allows it to be toxic or antifeedant by the termite so that forced feeding activity is disrupted and causes death.

The feeding system that presents termites with only one option (no-choice test) allows for the mechanism of weight loss value differences in test samples; for instance, at the initial stage, termites will adjust to the provided living environment, resulting in low feeding activity. Termites that cannot adapt will die. Termites that successfully adjust to the provided environment will engage in food orientation. This type of orientation can occur randomly and due to certain influences, such as a scent coming from the food provided. Next, the termites try to taste the food provided by biting into the surface of the food. If that part is not suitable, the termites will move on to another section until they find an appropriate part that meets the food criteria. If the food is suitable, the termites will continue to eat. Conversely, if the food does not meet the criteria, the termites will leave the provided food and choose not to eat. Weak termites will gradually die off [28].

CONCLUSION

The abundance of terpenoid compounds in the essential oil of *L. angulata* significantly influences its anti-termite activity against *M. gilvus*, achieving a mortality rate of 84%. This effectiveness positions it as a promising candidate for further research, particularly in field applications, to evaluate its potential as an environmentally friendly botanical pesticide. Additionally, optimizing the essential oil concentration is crucial, as the current study has not reached a 100% mortality rate in the tested termite population. Future investigations are expected to enhance the understanding of this essential oil's efficacy and mechanisms of action in termite control.

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